

According to research reports half of the students believed that information technology improved the courses that they were taking while most preferred a 'moderate' level of IT usage in their courses. There appeared here possibly to be a concern about 'excessive' use of information technology, though the study did not explore this area further.

The use of information technology by students in their daily lives is increasing and while many instructors are using IT effectively in their courses, it appears that many are not, revealing significant opportunity for improvement.

Categorization of information technology tools for education:

The information technology based tools that can be used for education are expanding daily. The following chart illustrates the technologies available:

Academic Year	Ways in which ICT tools were used
1998/99	Course notes/tutorial exercises available on website. Students expected to prepare for classroom sessions and to use e-mail to communicate with the tutor.
1999/00	Web pages supplemented by interactive tutorials on CD, on-line tests for formative purposes and asynchronous discussion board.
2000/01	Coursework for the first time explicitly linked to the

	interactive tutorials. FAQtool introduced. To support coursework.
2001/02	Module materials and communications packaged in the VLE Blackboard. Use of asynchronous discussion boards linked to coursework and also directly assessed.

ICT: changes the continuing training:

Recently the role of higher education institutions in the area of training of employees is limited. The increasing use of ICT could mean a change in this respect. The potential changes because of ICT depend on the extent to which:

- ICT (is)/(will be) used as a training tool for training of employees. If the role of ICT is limited, than expected changes in the structure of the market because of this will be limited;
- ICT as a training tool can be considered as additional training in the sense that ICT helps to organize training institutions where otherwise no training would have taken place. Points 1 and 2 together determine to what extent the market of training of employees grows as a whole because of the use of ICT as a training tool.
- The use of ICT could improve the relative position of higher education institutions in this market. The potential changes for higher education institutions because of ICT will be higher, the more important this training tool turns out to be, the more this will lead to

additional training and the more this will change their market position compared to other suppliers.

The importance of ICT as a training tool:

In the Netherlands NIDAP organizes a yearly survey on continuing training among approximately 800 companies with at least 50 employees. For the survey over 1999, we made use of the possibility to add a number of questions to this survey about their use of ICT-based training. The outcomes of the survey lead to the following estimates for the quantitative use of ICT-based training of the employed.

Proportion of larger companies (>50) using ICT as a training tool	32%
Proportion of larger companies (>50) using a CBT as a training tool	23%
Number of employees trained through ICT (including extrapolated figures for smaller companies)	300.000
Participants in training through ICT as a proportion of all trained employees	12%

The following table presents the utilization of the web in the organization of teaching:

Use made of the web	(%) of response
Information on course homepages	70%
Submitting assignments to teacher	50%
Course administration applications	60%
Monitoring points for partial completion	50%
Giving feedback for improvement of course or teaching	30%
Distribution channel for course material	70%

Benefits/Advantages of ICT in Education:

Here are some of the benefits which ICT brings to education according to recent research findings.

- Greater efficiency throughout the school.
- Communication channels are increased through email, discussion groups and chat rooms
- Regular use of ICT across different curriculum subjects can have a beneficial motivational influence on students' learning.
- ICT facilitates sharing of resources, expertise and advice
- Greater flexibility in when and where tasks are carried out

- Gains in ICT literacy skills, confidence and enthusiasm.
- Easier planning and preparation of lessons and designing materials
- Access to up-to-date pupil and school data, anytime and anywhere.
- Enhancement of professional image projected to colleagues.
- Students are generally more 'on task' and express more positive feelings when they use computers than when they are given other tasks to do.
- Computer use during lessons motivated students to continue using learning outside school hours.

Benefits for students:

- Higher quality lessons through greater collaboration between teachers in planning and preparing resources.
- More focused teaching, tailored to students' strengths and weaknesses, through better analysis of attainment data
- Improved pastoral care and behaviour management through better tracking of students
- Gains in understanding and analytical skills, including improvements in reading comprehension.
- Development of writing skills (including spelling, grammar, punctuation, editing and re-drafting), also fluency, originality and elaboration.
- Encouragement of independent and active learning, and self-responsibility for learning.
- Flexibility of 'anytime, anywhere' access (Jacobsen and Kremer, 2000)
- Development of higher level learning styles.

- Students who used educational technology in school felt more successful in school, were more motivated to learn and have increased self-confidence and self-esteem
- Students found learning in a technology-enhanced setting more stimulating and student-centred than in a traditional classroom
- Broadband technology supports the reliable and uninterrupted downloading of web-hosted educational multimedia resources
- Opportunities to address their work to an external audience
- Opportunities to collaborate on assignments with people outside or inside school

Benefits for parents:

- Easier communication with teachers
- Higher quality student reports – more legible, more detailed, better presented
- Greater access to more accurate attendance and attainment information
- Increased involvement in education for parents and, in some cases, improved self-esteem
- Increased knowledge of children's learning and capabilities, owing to increase in learning activity being situated in the home
- Parents are more likely to be engaged in the school community

Disadvantages of ICT:

One of the major barriers for the cause of ICT not reaching its full potential in the foundation stage is teacher's attitude. According to Hara (2004), within the early years education attitudes towards ICT can

vary considerably. Some see it as a potential tool to aid learning whereas others seem to disagree with the use of technology in early year settings. Blatchford and Whitebread (2003:16), suggests that the use of ICT in the foundation stage is “unhealthy and hinders learning”. Other early years educators who are opposed to offering ICT experiences within the educational settings take a less extreme view than this and suggest that ICT is fine, but there are other more vital experiences that young children will benefit from, (Blatchford and Whitebread, 2003). In theory some people may have the opinion that the teachers who had not experienced ICT throughout their learning tend to have a negative attitude towards it, as they may lack the training in that area of the curriculum.

Another important drawback to using ICT in schools is the fact that computers are expensive. According to the IT learning exchange (2001), in most schools ICT will be the single largest curriculum budget cost. This may be seen as a good thing but on the other hand there will be little money left over for other significant costs

Recommendations:

- The teachers should increase the use of ICT for content transaction, preparation of the teaching-learning materials, academic planning, project work and making presentations as these are the components directly related to the teaching-learning process, rather than using it for maintaining records, examination purpose and downloading information. For the fulfillment of this objective, training programmes need to be conducted on a large scale.

- The management should encourage and support the schools to develop language laboratory and use it for the teaching of languages.
- The management should motivate teachers to use ICT for the teaching-learning process by providing the incentives and framing the policies at the institute.
- Govt. and other ICT companies should collaborate with Teacher Education colleges to provide training to in-service teachers for using ICT in teaching-learning process.
- Number of teachers attending workshops and seminars on “the Use of ICT in the teaching-learning process” should increase. Individual and institutions should utilize such opportunities to the maximum.
- Schools should prepare a schedule for a regular access to computers by students for preparing projects and assignments.
- Teachers should not restrict their knowledge and expertise of using computers for their own professional growth and development but should plan out activities for contributing to the growth and development of the institution.

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